

The difficulties of public school teachers while implementing Single National Curriculum

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Abstract

The purpose of teacher's professional development is gaining new skills through continuing education and trainings. It is important because it has the potential to open opportunities for the teachers as well as for the student's career. The purpose of this study is to find out the problems faced by English teachers in teaching the Single National Curriculum in public schools of Lahore. The study has been taken twelve public schools of Lahore. The aim of this research is to examine the challenges faced by English schools teachers while teaching the Single National Curriculum. One of the significant reasons of this research is to know about teachers experience while teaching the English of Single National Curriculum. The present study used the mixed methods to prepare the report in which data has been collected. The Quantitative data is based on questionnaires that have been taken from forty English schools teachers of Lahore and compiled into SPSS. The data has been explored through descriptive analysis using percentages and statistics. The Qualitative data is used in this study are based on previous literature and sample work collected by participants. The semi structured interviews have been taken from eight public schools teachers and written narrative from six English teachers. The researcher had collected the data then analyzed through coding and thematic analysis. The findings show that English teachers are facing difficulties in implementing the Single National Curriculum in public schools. There are some learning problems in pronunciation, lack of trainings, lack of resources, teaching skills and methods. They are also facing the problems of their teaching skills without proper trainings. There is lack of resources too which make difficult for teachers to implement a Single National Curriculum properly.

Keywords: pedagogical skills, methodology, resources, lack of teacher training.

Introduction

English as a second language in Pakistan

“Second language learning and identity construction” has acquired the status of most important subject of research (Canagarajah, 1999). Language is not only the tool communication for the learners but it also reinforces their identity as who they are, and how they stand in relationship to the world. (Norton, 2000) English language is the life blood of communication worldwide. (Ahmed, Rao, 2012). As a result, it becomes pertinent to learn English language in order to flourish and prosper in their academic and professional lives (Muhammad, 2011).

It needs yet to be seen how English as a second language as the most popular official language and a standardized mode of instruction (MOI) is inculcated as part of teacher’s training modules as part of professional development in Pakistan. While primary and secondary education is the bedrock for academic development whereas, higher education familiarizes and inculcates novel ideas in people who would later play the roles of leaders and act as harbinger of change. Exposure to higher education maps out the economic standing of a nation and directs the policymakers of the country in the futuristic direction (Government of Pakistan, 2005).

What is professional development for teacher?

Teacher professional development is the ongoing education for educators. It is the way teachers can improve their teaching skills and boost the knowledge of student. Learning can take place in two settings one is formal and other is informal. Formal settings include conferences, courses, seminars, retreats and workshops. Informal opportunities for teacher professional development include independent research or investigation, peer learning initiatives or even just chatting with a colleague in the staff room. Professional development for teachers takes place on

a number of different levels among teachers in a given school and in a classroom or individual basis.

Why training is important?

Training is very important for the professional development of teacher that enables the teachers to learn knowledge and skills to improve their performance. It plays an important role for the improvement of student's knowledge. The development of a teacher's competency is in no way limited to the educators engaged in higher education; in fact, a teacher's competency to consciously improve and evolve is one of the greatest significations. A teacher's competence can affect values, behaviours, communication, aims, and practices. They can also uplift professional development and curricular studies. (Selvi, 2010). Competencies can be defined as "the set of knowledge, skills, and experience necessary for future, which manifests in activities" (Katane et.al. 44). Fakhra (2012) defined teacher's competencies as knowledge and skills of teachers which are required for fruitful quality education at the higher level.

Vision for the Assessment of English Curriculum

English is always been considered an important and good skill in education at all levels and the level of international communication and for individual development for a better future. English is an important medium for the students to talk or communicate effectively with other people both in writing and orally. Learning a second language provides students the opportunities of social, cultural, intellectual, emotional and material knowledge that is useful for building a multicultural society. The Single National Curriculum 2006 has been revised at various stages due to the changing demand at global and local levels. A first review is conducted at the Islamabad Capital Territory (ICT) level in 2017 to update the ICT curriculum for schools. In 2019, the government's current vision is to develop the one curriculum for all education

sectors in the country. As a result, there are two areas for improvement found i.e. procedures of assessment and teaching processes. English Teachers should provide the necessary skills to complement the textbooks and other resources and should pay special attention to the skills, i.e., speaking, reading, writing and listening to the students. It is believed that these essential goals outlined in the Single National Curriculum fill this gap.

Literature review

What is teaching?

Teaching is a skill that encompasses facilitating learners to learn effectively; it is performance and competence at the same time. Significant research has been done globally in this particular field, new methods, techniques, and innovations in teaching and learning are being discovered regularly. It is almost an established fact that there is a tangible constructive correlation between the proficiency and qualifications of the teacher and the learning and achievement of the students. To be able to enhance the quality and effectiveness of the teachers and to further cultivate their skill set in teaching, teachers' training programs have become part of all educational departments. Presently, the burning issue in higher education may be the lack of reliability and obsolete teaching methodologies of the teachers and their inability to engage the students in the learning process. Moreover, the faculty engaged in universities enters the arena of teaching with no prior professional training. The lack of professional training of educators keeps them ignorant of the process through which learning truly occurs and its impact that directly affects students' learning. They fail to understand how university students grow academically and the effects of the university exposure on them.

The fact must be acknowledged that teachers need rigorous training and stamina to come up to the mark. A teacher is a person who is expected to be ethically dedicated to his/her work, someone who is not only subject to perform the duty of teaching others but also is required to acquire firsthand knowledge to keep up with modern knowledge, new techniques and methodologies in the field of education.

Deficiency of development and Training

The institutions of education do not spend some available funds for the development of teachers and training. They do not want to send to organize and conduct workshops, seminars, courses and conferences to develop themselves and learn modern and contemporary methodologies and teaching methods. Few teachers are selected for training, and most teachers are not given the opportunity to improve their teaching skills. It is an important and essential for quality work that Teaching is hard work. There is a lack of training opportunities for teachers in Pakistan. There are many educational institutions in the country and these institutions are either under-resourced or poorly managed due to lack of funds and trained personnel like the trainers and administrators. “Several studies showing that the most significant school-based factor is the quality of teacher’s achievement of students” (Mincu, 2015).

There are no real libraries where students can study and read books. Books are extinct and unavailable. There are no modern electronic libraries in the library; especially government schools do not have computer equipment. Neither adequate lighting nor generators can make learning comfortable for ambitious and motivated students in case of load and power outages. The Overcrowded classrooms, corridors full of students, inadequate teachers, laboratories without the necessary equipment for practical teaching and learning lead to low quality and hopelessness of education (Louis, 1987).

Low budgetary allotment for education

The system of education in Pakistan has been paralyzed due to allocation of funds and resources in the budget. The budget of education which is certainly not enough to meet the growing needs of the population, inclusion of modern and advanced technology in the education system and high taxes, low wages are also obstacles to the expansion of this sector. Hourly fees

for visiting teachers are also taxed at the expense of 10 percent of applicants and 20 percent of non-applicants, which are truly unfair and reduces the limited revenue.

In many countries such as Sri Lanka and Bangladesh the share of education in the total budget of the country is increasing but in Pakistan it is steadily decreasing (Sian, 2012).

Methodology

Population of the Study

This study is considered a group for a study or statistical reasoning. The target population of the study is twelve Public sectors. The written Narratives have been filled from six female teachers at public schools of Lahore. The questionnaires have been filled from forty female teachers at public schools of Lahore. This research is based on probability sampling as the subjects of population are selected randomly for achieving the objective of research. Open ended and semi structured interviews have been taken from eight teachers of public schools. The purpose of choosing government school teachers is to know about their difficulties while teaching English of Single National Curriculum. They are facing the difficulties in teaching and implications in teaching the Single National Curriculum.

Research Instruments

Three tools are used to conduct the study to get the results in better way.

1. Quantitative data has been collected through the questionnaires of close ended from the forty teachers of public schools of Lahore.
2. Qualitative data is based on semi structured open ended interviews and probes that have been taken from the eight teachers of public schools of Lahore.
3. Written narrative has been taken from six teachers to know about teacher's experiences of teaching while teaching English the Single National Curriculum (SNC).

The collection of data is based on questionnaire which is close ended from the teachers at public schools of Lahore. Then the data has been collected through interviews unstructured, open

ended protocol from the teachers of public schools. Written narrative is used to know about teachers experiences of teaching about Single National Curriculum (SNC). The following two categories of research methodology exist; Qualitative and Quantitative. In qualitative research, information is acquired through conversational techniques, open ended questions and face to face interaction. The collection of responses is not numerical.

Aims and Objectives

1. To evaluate the difficulties of English teachers of public schools of Lahore at primary level through structured interviews of teachers.
2. To identify the challenges confronting by public school teachers of Lahore while teaching English of Single National Curriculum (SNC) through unstructured interviews.
3. To discover experiences of teachers in written narrative of Single National Curriculum at primary level of public schools of Lahore.

Research questions

- Q1.** What are the views of the public-school teachers of Lahore implementing on the Single National Curriculum?
- Q2.** What type of problems public school teachers faced while teaching English of the Single National Curriculum (SNC)?
- Q3.** What would be the experiences of teachers regarding teaching the Single National Curriculum (SNC) at the primary level in public schools in Lahore?

Justification of study

The aim of this research is to examine the difficulties of English school teachers while teaching Single National Curriculum in government schools of Lahore. There are semi-structured protocols interviews, questionnaires and written narratives of teachers of public schools in Lahore. The aim of this study is to provide teachers' perspectives on teaching the Single National Curriculum (SNC). One of the significant reasons of this research is to learn about teacher experience while teaching the Single National Curriculum. Do English teachers have the teaching skills and methodology? Is there lack of teaching skills in government schools in Lahore? What are the implications coming for teachers in teaching English?

Statement of Problem

The public-school teachers are facing challenges in implementing the Single National Curriculum (SNC) in classroom skills of teaching, lesson planning, teaching methods, lack of resources and some barriers of teaching in public schools of Lahore. Lack of teaching skills and teacher training are major problems for teachers. The focus of this study is to know about the implications of the public school teachers about Single National Curriculum.

The primary role of teacher is to teach and support the students in learning and general understanding of the English material. Pakistan is facing some major challenges in terms of educational programs. The main challenge is the development of teacher training. Training institutions for teachers are also facing financial difficulties. There are shortage of funds, teaching aids and text materials and other some related resources in educational institutions. This research shows that teacher education programs are facing significant challenges in terms of quality, lack of resources and policy. One of the most important problems identified by the study is the lack of training of public school teachers. Teachers have no clear idea about how to plan

lessons to teach the Single National Curriculum. The term teaching methods refers to the general principles, teaching and management strategies using in classroom learning.

This study is designed to explore the impact of Single National Curriculum of public schools of Lahore. Teachers have awareness of teaching methods but they are not properly trained about it and how to apply these methods in the classroom. Teachers are facing difficulties in teaching English because they are not trained. There is also lack of resources in government schools. The purpose of this study is to find out the problems of teachers.

Findings of Quantitative Data

This part of the chapter analyzes and discusses quantitative data. All data containing participants' responses is carefully coded and compiled into SPSS. The data has been explored through descriptive analysis using percentages and statistics. The research of quantitative is an organized method of collecting information and examining it for decision making. This data is related to numbers. By having more information to study, more accurate results can be obtained by having in depth information of the study. Closed queries are used in this research method because researchers usually want to collect statistical data. There are various tools that are used

quantitative methods to collect the data.

On Table one, Respondents who answered questions 1 to 6 are feeling encouraging and motivating because they have the skills and new methods. Teaching is very important for the teaching of the National Curriculum. The questions about skills and teaching methods were highly motivated from respondents. However the highest percentage makes evident the most rampant value out of the 40 respondents. 70% strongly agree, 20% agree, 7% moderately agree and 3% disagree on the importance of skills and teaching methods. According to these results, teaching skills and new methods are very important for the teaching of the Single National Curriculum. Skills play an important role in learning SNC. It is very useful for teaching both teachers and students.

On Table 2, respondents who answered questions seven to twelve also showed enthusiasm and great help in having the resources to teach the CNC. These responses show that resources play an important role in teaching the CNC. It is more useful for teaching curriculum and easy to understand for students. However, the highest percentage makes clear the most rampant meaning: 50% strongly agree, 30% agree, 15% disagree, and 5% strongly disagree. So, 80% of the answers show that the resources are useful for learning and make things simpler and more conceptual. The government should provide resources to help teachers and students. Public schools lack resources.

On Table three, respondents answering questions thirteen to twenty show that teacher training is also very important for teachers. The One National Curriculum is easier to teach to public school teachers after training. However, the highest percentage makes evident the most rampant value of the 70% who fully agree that teacher training for public school teachers is very necessary. 20% agree and 10% disagree. Teaching is an important part for English teachers. According to these responses, this shows that learning is beneficial for teachers and makes teaching easier. This is very helpful for both teachers and students. The government must take steps to overcome barriers to improve student achievement in public schools. They must train public school teachers at least once a month. According to these responses, the CNC is not easy, especially for older, untrained teachers. This shows that learning is very important and improves the knowledge of public-school teachers.

Finding the Qualitative data

The qualitative data is used in this study are based on previous literature and sample work collected by participants. The researcher has been collected the data from interviews and written narrative then used coding to analyze the narrative and interview data. Quality research is a process associated with an inquiry. The findings of qualitative data will helps to create a complete understanding of issues or problems in their natural language. Qualitative research is a non-statistical method.

Qualitative research largely depends on the experience of the researchers and the questions used to study the sample. The sample size is limited to eight female teachers. Questions are open ended asked in such a way that another question or set of questions arises. The written narrative has been taken from six teachers. The purpose of all collecting data from protocol is to collect information from a sample.

Thematic analysis of Study

Theme	Sub-Theme	Descriptive Codes
Teachers are facing problems to teach SNC	Lack of trainings	Teachers understand the concept of English SNC but feel difficult to deliver in a large class.
		Teachers have knowledge but find it difficult to deliver in class.
	Lack of new Methodology	They feel difficulties to teach absent students.
		Students don't take interest learn or listen the teachers.
	Lack of Management	There is a shortage of teachers. It creates a hurdle for teachers to manage two classes together.
		Students face difficulties listening to the teacher in this way.
	Lake of Resources	Teachers feel difficulties to speak English with students.
		They are unable to deliver lecture in English and found difficult to make them understand.
		There are no resources that make the lecture understand in better way.
		Teachers have no funds or resources that can be used for students.

Encoding is a qualitative data analysis strategy in which some characteristics of the data are given a meaningful label that allows the researcher to recognize the relevant content that encompasses the data. It is the process of organizing and labeling the qualitative data to bring out the various relationships and themes between them. The researcher is used coding to analyze all qualitative data. According to the research, coding shows that teaching skills are necessary and are very important for teaching any subject. If teachers have proper English language skills and methods, it is easy to understand and make students understand correctly.

Conclusion

To conclude the research, researcher agrees on this point that in education progress is almost impossible without action in education. The growth and development of education, the support provided by teachers are directly related to all socio-economic development and progress. The youth and good-hearted minds of a community or country are shaped, guided and transformed by teachers because teacher plays an important role in the education of every child life. A good teacher may have all the things which are helpful for the student's future. There must be trainings from government for the teachers. It is useful for the future of students that they learn new things from up-to-date resources. Resources are useful for increasing of knowledge in their life. It helped to improve their knowledge and from new methodologies they will clear their concepts and knowledge in better way. In Islam, the duties of the teacher are better defined and he or she is given significant responsibility for the growth of their charges. This great value placed on teachers calls for improved teacher education especially teacher training, which is an essential component of teacher education. There are a number of serious problems with teacher training such as finding qualified teaching candidates, providing them with the necessary and correct skills, lack of resources in pedagogical institutions, teachers

discouraged from doing their job well, uneven distribution of qualified and effective teachers, dual education system, etc. etc. However practical measures such as spending money, rooting out corruption, and supporting institutions can help modernize teacher training in Pakistan. Despite a thorough evaluation of the literature, a weak point of the study is the reference to the difficulties of teacher training in general. The research suggests that there is a need for training in areas that are specific to the subject. In addition, a deeper understanding of the subject requires a thorough systematic study of the literature and empirical research. To conclude the all, it is found that the teachers should have the facilities for the proper teaching of English in public schools. Teachers have no proper trainings and facilities from government. In this way they are facing the problems to teach the students of public school students. The teachers must be trained regularly; only then other changes can come into education system and can really impact students positively.

Future recommendations

The following recommendations were put forward as one of the reasons for the results of this study:

- 1.** Before and after the introduction of SNC, refresher courses should be offered to improve the skills of teachers so that teachers can cope with the difficulties they will face and overcome their resistance to SNC.
- 2.** Print and electronic media should be used to spread the word about the importance of SNC.
- 3.** More funds need to be allocated to address the lack of resources in schools so that SNC can be effectively implemented.
- 4.** Teachers and students should be rewarded and recognized for their efforts to help develop a sense of camaraderie and enthusiasm for implementation at the primary school level.

5. According to this recommendation, SNC should be fully implemented in all education systems to ensure quality education.

6. Additional actions need to be taken to address Education for All issues, such as providing financial assistance to students from low-income families in the form of scholarships and recognizing and rewarding students with exceptional abilities.

The system of education and teacher training is facing many difficulties and challenges in Pakistan. There is always room for improvement. A democratic community and a society and a society where human development and education are highly valued teacher education and issues related to the quality of teachers are always a priority. (Cochran-Smith and Zeichner) Since Pakistan is on the path to democracy serious efforts and effort should be made in regard to teacher education. When teacher get the teachers trainings it give the opportunities for professional development to learn new things, methods and the ways, strategies, skills etc. when teacher get skills the automatically feel confident and motivated and happy to attain best things for their students. If the teacher will be happy and confident students automatically fell comfortable with their teachers and studies. Teachers training programs not only impact teachers but students too. Only a one teacher who is fully skilled can go on impact many or thousand students. He or She has a big role to play in nation building because students are the citizens of tomorrow.

The discovery and results of the study indicated that teacher training issues could be addressed by securing government ownership and building trust and accountability in school systems, minimizing political interference, and respecting merit in teacher recruitment and provision Facilities for teachers and teacher training in Pakistan.

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